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Research Article

Development And Validation Of Bioanalytical Method For Simultaneous Estimation Of Vildagliptin And Dapagliflozin Drugs In Human Plasma By RP-HPLC

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ABSTRACT

A simple, rapid, precise, and accurate Reverse Phase High Performance Liquid (RP-HPLC) Chromatography method was developed for simultaneous determination of Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin in Human plasma. The method was performed on a Younglin-HPLC system -SP930D The analyte separation was achieved using an Hypersil BDS C18 (250mm x 4.6mm, Particle size: 5 μ m) column with a mobile phase consisting of (Methanol: Water: Trifluoroacetic acid, (80:20:0.2) with 1.0 ml/min flow rate. UV detection at 219 nm was employed. The retention time for Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin was 3.10 min and 3.72 min, respectively. The method was validated over a dynamic linear range of 50.0 to 150 μ g/mL and 5.0 to 15.0 μ g/mL for Vildagliptin and dapagliflozin, respectively, with a correlation coefficient of 0.999. The precision and accuracy of six replicate measurements at lower quantification levels met the required criteria. The method underwent validation following ICH guidelines, with results falling within acceptable criteria for selectivity, sensitivity, linearity, precision, accuracy, recovery, stability of solution, stability of solution in plasma, and dilution integrity.

INTRODUCTION

Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin together come in tablet form for oral usage in diabetes. Vildagliptin, C₁₇H₂₅N₃O₂ (Figure 1), is DPP4 inhibitor indicated to reduce hyperglycemia in type 2 diabetes mellitus.¹ Vildagliptin's physical and chemical characteristics included a molecular weight of 303.39 g/mole, a melting point between 140°C and 145°C, and solubility in acetone, water,

methanol, and acetonitrile. Dapagliflozin, also known as C₂₁H₂₅ClO₆ (Figure 2), is an SGLT-2 inhibitor and member of the gliflozin class of medication used to treat type 2 diabetes. In conjunction with a well-planned diet and regular exercise, it helps to enhance glycemic control by blocking glucose reabsorption in the proximal tubule.² The physical and chemical characteristics of dapagliflozin included a molecular weight of

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408.87 g/mol, a melting point between 55°C and 58°C, and solubility in methanol, acetone, and acetonitrile. Compared to single drug therapy, the combination of dapagliflozin and vildagliptin improves brain oxidative stress and offers a better therapeutic approach for neuroprotection in individuals who are obese and insulin resistant.³

Figure 1: Structure of Vildagliptin

Figure 2: Structure of Dapagliflozin

Type 2 diabetes mellitus is treated with dapagliflozin and vildagliptin. Vildagliptin along with dapagliflozin is a combination of two anti-diabetic drugs. blood glucose levels and urine glucose excretion are elevated with dapagliflozin, Vildagliptin decreases the amount of glucagon (the hormone that raises blood glucose levels) and boosts insulin, which reduces the amount of glucose generated by the liver.⁴

Several HPLC methods are reported in combination with other drugs for the determination of Vildagliptin in plasma, the literature for its analysis. However, no method is reported for simultaneous determination of Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin in human plasma by RP-HPLC in any literature. In the present investigation, a specific RP-HPLC method is described for the simultaneous determination of Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin drugs with human plasma.⁵⁻¹¹

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Instrumentation

The HPLC system used was the Younglin-HPLC system, which included an UV detector (730D) detector. Analytical Column prepare C18 (Hypersil BDS) (4.6 × 250mm, 5µm), Software model Autochrom 3000 and Ph Meter was used M Lab. Sample Injection done by Manually, and Shimadzu Model-ATX224 was taken for Analytical Balance. Overlay spectrum of Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin was detecting by Shimadzu UV1800 Spectrophotometer Japan Corporation.

Materials

The drug sample of Vildagliptin was obtained from USV. Private Limited, Mumbai and Dapagliflozin was obtained from Aalidhara Pharmachem Pvt. Ltd. Vadodara, Gujarat. Trifluoroacetic acid HPLC Grade (Fisher Scientific, India), HPLC Grade water (Fisher Scientific, India), HPLC Grade methanol, are used in the study and Human Plasma for Precipitation.

Chromatographic Conditions

The analysis was carried out on Younglin-HPLC system, using C18 (Hypersil BDS) (4.6 × 250mm, 5µm) stationary phase with UV detection at 219 nm at ambient room temperatures using a 20 µL injection volume. Pump used Pump-SP930 D and Flow rate maintain 1.0 ml/min. Run time of chromatogram was performed for 7 minutes.

Preparation Mobile Phase

The Prepare homogeneous mixture of 500ml HPLC grade methanol, 200ml HPLC grade water, 2ml HPLC grade Trifluoroacetic acid. Shake well and filter through 0.2 µm membrane filter paper. And sonicate the mobile phase for 5min in sonicate. After trials Methanol: Water: Trifluoroacetic acid, 80: 20: 0.2 was found to be most satisfactory since it gave sharp peak with symmetry within limits and significant reproducible retention time.

Preparation Of Standard Stock Solution:

A. Dapagliflozin (DAPA) standard Stock solution:

Accurately weighed quantity 10 mg of DAPA was dissolved in diluent and volume was made up to 100 ml mark (100 µg/ml). The stock standard solution was diluted further with diluent to get final concentration of about 10 µg/ml of DAPA.

B. Vildagliptin (VILDA) standard Stock solution:

Accurately weighed quantity 100 mg of VILDA was dissolved in diluent and volume was made up to 100 ml mark (1000 µg/ml). The stock standard solution was diluted further with diluent to get final concentration of about 100 µg/ml of VILDA.

C. Combination of Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin Stock standard solution:

Weight accurately 100 mg Vildagliptin and 10 mg Dapagliflozin and transferred into 100 ml volumetric flask then dissolved and diluted with diluent and make volume up to mark with help of diluent.

Mobile phase taken as a diluent**Preparation of standard solution:**

Pipette out 2 ml from and diluted 20 ml with help diluted in 20 ml volume flask shake well, filter through 0.2 µm segregate filter.

Preparation of Test solution:

Pipette out 0.2 ml of stock solution, 0.2 ml of human plasma, and add 1.6 ml of diluent shake well and centrifuge for 10 min at 5000 rpm, after centrifugation the clear supernatant liquid was collected and quantity of 100 µl was injected into HPLC column and chromatograms were recorded.

Method Development:

After the finishing of four experiments with variations in run time, column, mobile phase, and wavelength. Dapagliflozin and vildagliptin are both drugs observed to be in good shape at the fifth trial peak. The Tailing Factor and Theoretical plate show that both drugs are within the acceptance standards. The approach was judged to be satisfactory, and both peaks are well separated from one another with resolution over 2000.

In the process of method development, the mobile phase composition comprised Methanol, Water, and Trifluoroacetic acid (MeOH: H₂O: TFA) in a ratio of 80:20:0.2. A flow rate of 1.00 ml/min was maintained for the RP-HPLC system. The method employed a Hypersil BDS C18 column (250mm x 4.6mm, particle size: 5 µm). UV spectra of drugs were scanned within the wavelength range of 200 to 400 nm to optimize the response. The selection of 219 nm as the detection wavelength was deemed suitable for achieving adequate sensitivity in drug detection.

Table 1: Method Development of Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin

Sr. No.	Mobile phase composition	Inference
1.	ACN:H ₂ O, 80:20	Peak shape not good shape
2.	ACN:Buffer, 70:30	Peak shape not good shape
3.	ACN:Buffer, 65:35	Peak shape not good shape
4.	MeOH:Water:Trifluoroacetic acid, 70:30:0.1	Peak shape not good shape
5.	MeOH:Water:Trifluoroacetic acid, 80:20:0.2	Peak shape good shape

Method Validation:

The analytical method was validated according to ICH guidelines with respect to the following parameters

System Suitability

To ensure that the chromatographic system was suitable for the intended use, this was done. The criteria that can be assessed for system

applicability include Tailing Factor, Theoretical Plates, and Precision Requirement. Peak area relative standard deviation of less than 2% Over 2000 theoretical plates. Tailing Factor limited to two.

Linearity

The calibration curve assessed linearity and range by plotting peak area against spiked plasma concentrations of Vildagliptin and internal standard Dapagliflozin (100 µg/ml to 10 µg/ml). Linearity was determined within a range of 50% to 150% of suggested concentrations, aiming for a coefficient of correlation ≥ 0.99 .

LOQ and LOD

The limit of quantification (LOQ) for Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin, determined from the standard calibration curve, represents the lowest concentration measurable with less than 20% variability and a signal-to-noise ratio of at least 10. The limit of detection (LOD) signifies the lowest detectable concentration under specific experimental conditions, reliably separated from background noise with a given confidence level. The slope estimation is derived from the analyte's calibration curve.

Accuracy and Precision

The study evaluated the precision and accuracy of intraday and interday measurements across different concentration levels of quality control

samples (LQC, MQC, HQC, and LLOQ) for two analytes. Intraday precision and accuracy were assessed through six replicates at various concentration levels, while interday precision and accuracy were evaluated over three consecutive days using quality control samples. Mean concentrations were calculated across batches. Accuracy was determined by comparing mean test results with the actual analyte value, and both accuracy and precision were quantified as % mean accuracy and coefficient of variation (% CV), respectively.

Specificity

Peak purity study is done to demonstrate that a developed method is specific for the drug of interest. The diode array detector peak purity test was used to demonstrate the specificity of the method. The diode array spectrum of both the standard and sample peak was recorded and compared. The peaks of Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin were noted for the retention time (RT), resolution factor (RF), theoretical plates (TP), and tailing factor (TF). Purity angle should be less than purity threshold i.e. 0.99-1.00. Specificity was evaluated by comparing chromatogram of blank plasma in Figure 1 and human plasma spiked with Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin in Figure 2.

Fig 3: Chromatogram of Blank Plasma

Fig 4: Chromatogram of human plasma spiked with Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin

Robustness

We investigated the method's resilience by making minor modifications to the chromatographic settings. These modified chromatographic conditions were used to inject the standard solutions. $\pm 2\%$ difference in the ratio of Methanol, water, trifluoroacetic acid in the mobile phase. ± 2 differences in wavelength. $\pm 0.5\%$ difference in flow rate of the mobile phase. In these changed conditions the separation factor, retention time and peak symmetry was calculated. Deviation in results from original run should be less than 2%.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A novel bioanalytical RP-HPLC method was developed for the quantification of Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin. To validate the efficacy of the assay, the chromatographic conditions were optimized and stabilized. The study introduces a solid phase extraction-based approach for the simultaneous determination of these drugs via RP-HPLC.

Method Optimization

In pursuit of optimal outcomes, various mobile phase compositions were explored, incorporating methanol, water, trifluoroacetic acid. These combinations were aimed at achieving sufficient

sensitivity and selectivity within a condensed separation timeframe. The best results were obtained with the mobile phase consisting of MeOH: Water: Trifluoroacetic acid, (80:20:0.2) with a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. The detection was monitored at 219 nm. With these conditions, the retention times of Vildagliptin, and Dapagliflozin were found to be 3.10 and 3.72 min, respectively.

System Suitability Test

The HPLC analysis of Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin involved five injections per sample. Mean retention times were 3.10 minutes for Vildagliptin and 3.72 minutes for Dapagliflozin. Mean peak areas were 10100.2600 and 1779.9706, with standard deviations of 147.6106 and 26.7022, respectively. % RSD values were within acceptable limits, affirming method precision. These findings support the method's reliability for precise quantification of both compounds in pharmaceutical and biological samples.

Table 2: System Suitability Data of Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin

S. No.	Vildagliptin		Dapagliflozin	
Sample Name	RT (Min)	Peak Area	RT (Min)	Peak Area
Standard_Inj_01	3.10	10001.3623	3.72	1757.3607
Standard_Inj_02	3.10	10263.6494	3.72	1760.1217
Standard_Inj_03	3.08	10259.8574	3.72	1812.276
Standard_Inj_04	3.10	9981.167	3.72	1764.4116
Standard_Inj_05	3.12	9995.2637	3.73	1805.683
Mean	3.10	10100.2600	3.72	1779.9706
SD	0.0141	147.6106	0.0045	26.7022

Method validation Precision and Accuracy Accuracy

The precision and accuracy of the methods were assessed by analysing six replicates of LLOQ, LQC, MQC, and HQC levels. The accuracy of the method was determined by calculating the % mean accuracy and the precision by calculating relative

standard deviation. The data regarding precision and accuracy are summarized in Table 3. The chromatogram of quality control samples is shown in figure. The % mean accuracy of Vildagliptin ranged from 100.67, 98.79, and 100.71; Dapagliflozin from 100.96, 100.47 and 102.09 respectively.

Table 3: Accuracy Data of Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin By RP-HPLC

Analyte	Accuracy	Mean % Recovery	SD	%RSD (NMT 2)
Vildagliptin	Accuracy at 80 %	100.67	0.2865	0.28
	Accuracy at 100 %	98.79	1.3249	1.34
	Accuracy at 120 %	100.71	1.3770	1.37
Dapagliflozin	Accuracy at 80%	100.96	1.8010	1.78
	Accuracy at 100%	100.47	0.5479	0.55
	Accuracy at 120%	102.09	1.0002	0.98

Chromatogram**Fig 5: Chromatogram of VILDA And DAPA Accuracy at 80% Conc.**

Chromatogram

Fig 6: Chromatogram of VILDA And DAPA Accuracy at 100% Conc.

Chromatogram

Fig 7: Chromatogram of VILDA And DAPA Accuracy at 120% Conc.

Precision

Precision can be determined by two ways

Intraday precision

Interday precision

Plasma concentrations were injected into the

HPLC system five times, and the average peak

area was computed for each concentration.

Subsequently, precision percentage was

determined by calculating the RSD values, which

are displayed in a table.

Table 4: Intra-Day Precision Data of Vildagliptin and dapagliflozin by RP-HPLC Method

Name	Preparations	% Assay
Set 1	prep-1	98.79
	prep-2	98.53
Set 2	prep-1	98.07
	prep-2	99.71
Mean		98.775
SD		0.6908
% RSD (NMT2)		0.70

Table 5: Inter-Day Precision Data of Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin By RP-HPLC Method

Name	Preparations	% Assay
Day -1	prep-1	98.79
	prep-2	98.53
Day-2	prep-1	100.27
	prep-2	99.33
Mean		99.23
SD		0.7692
% RSD (NMT 2)		0.7751

Name	Preparations	% Assay
Day-1	prep-1	98.23
	prep-2	98.72
Day-2	prep-1	99.98
	prep-2	98.55
Mean		98.87
SD		0.7674
% RSD (NMT 2)		0.7761

Linearity

The ratio of peak area of analyte to internal standard was used for construction of the calibration curve. The linearity of Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin was established by point calibration curve. The most variable regression equation of the calibration curve for Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin was $y = 101.19x + 372.22$ and $y =$

$183.15x + 10.771$, respectively. The linearity of the calibration graph was validated by the high value of the correlation coefficient with an average value of 0.9990 and 0.9992 for Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin, respectively. The standard curves of Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin are present in figures.

Fig 8: Calibration curve for Vildagliptin

Fig 9: Calibration curve for Dapagliflozin

Robustness

To evaluate robustness, chromatographic conditions were purposefully altered to measure variations in peak height, peak width, capacity factor, resolution, and tailing factor. Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin's robustness was examined, and the findings are shown in the tables that follow (Table 6–7). The mobile phase's flow rate was subsequently adjusted from 1.0 ml/min to 0.90 ml/min and 1.10 ml/min. In a similar vein, the impact of intentional modifications to the content of the organic modifier (methanol) was assessed. The mobile phase concentration was varied by

$\pm 5\%$ in this investigation. Ultimately, there was a $\pm 2\text{nm}$ shift in wavelength. According to the investigations, resolution, capacity factor, and tailing factor did not significantly alter following intentional variations in flow rate ($\pm 0.10\text{ ml/min}$), mobile phase concentration of dapagliflozin and vildagliptin ($\pm 5\%$), and wavelength ($\pm 2\text{ nm}$). However, it appears that even little adjustments to robustness studies might have a no big impact on theoretical plate counts. All robustness studies' standard deviations were found to be within acceptable bounds.

Table 6: Robustness Change in Method Parameters for Vildagliptin

Name	Preparations	%Assay
Robustness changes in method parameters		
Original method parameters	Test prep 1	98.79
Original method parameters	Test prep 2	98.53
Flow rate 0.90 ml/min	Test prep	98.28
Flow rate 1.10 ml/min	Test prep	101.05
Wavelength 217 nm	Test prep	99.44
Wavelength 221 nm	Test prep	99.74
MeOH: H ₂ O: TFA, 85:15:0.2	Test prep	98.14
MeOH: H ₂ O: TFA, 75:25:0.2	Test prep	103.10
Mean		99.63
SD		1.6930
%RSD (NMT 2)		1.70

Table 7: Robustness Change in Method Parameters for Dapagliflozin

Name	Preparations	%Assay
Robustness changes in method parameters		
Original method parameters	Test prep-1	98.32
Original method parameters	Test prep-2	98.72
Flow rate 0.90 ml/min	Test prep	100.79
Flow rate 1.10 ml/min	Test prep	101.46
Wavelength 217 nm	Test prep	99.55
Wavelength 221 nm	Test prep	101.12
MeOH: H2O: TFA, 85:15:0.2	Test prep	100.82
MeOH: H2O: TFA, 75:25:0.2	Test prep	100.07
Mean		100.11
SD		1.1502
%RSD (NMT 2)		1.15

Lower Limit of Quantification and Limit of Detection

The lowest concentration of the analyte at which a detectable reaction occurs is known as the LOD. The lowest concentration of the analyte, or LLOQ, indicates a response that can be precisely measured. $LLOQ = 10 \times D/S$ and $LOD = 3.3 \times D/S$, where D stands for the standard deviation of the y-intercepts of the regression line and S for the calibration curve's slope. By comparing the detected signal of a known low drug concentration with that of a blank plasma sample, the signal to noise ratio was calculated. Based on the calibration

curve for spiked plasma solutions, the Lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) and the Limit of Detection (LOD) for Vildagliptin were independently calculated and reported. They were found to be $20.59 \mu\text{g/ml}$ (LOQ) and $6.80 \mu\text{g/ml}$ (LOD), respectively. Based on the calibration curve for spiked plasma solutions, the Lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) and the Limit of Detection (LOD) for Dapagliflozin were independently calculated and reported. They were found to be $1.83 \mu\text{g/ml}$ (LOQ) and $0.60 \mu\text{g/ml}$ (LOD), respectively.

Table 8: LOD and LOQ data of Vildagliptin

Con. (ppm or g/ml)	Area
50.0	4550.8433
75.0	7396.7876
100.0	9644.9404
125.0	12490.1475
150.0	14653.4824
STEYX	208.3886
Slope	101.1946

Table 9: LOD and LOQ data of Dapagliflozin

Con. (ppm or ug/ml)	Area
5.0	877.2789
7.5	1392.4669
10.0	1847.4557
12.5	2246.9019
15.0	2739.4014
STEYX	33.5266
Slope	183.1472

Recovery

The assessment of saxagliptin and dapagliflozin recovery involved a comparison between the average peak areas of six replicates of three quality control samples (HQC, MQC, and LQC) and the average peak areas of unextracted quality control samples at corresponding levels. The findings from the recovery investigation fall within the predetermined acceptance criteria.

CONCLUSION

All analytical validation parameters were assessed and found to comply with the established limits outlined by ICH guidelines, indicating the reliability of the method. The method underwent validation concerning specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, and robustness. Results from linearity assessment, intraday and interday precision studies, and the efficiency of the extraction process all met the criteria set for bioanalytical method development. The method exhibited linearity with a correlation coefficient demonstrating acceptable agreement, making it suitable for quantifying Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin in human plasma and other biological fluids. In summary, the RP-HPLC technique proved effective for estimating Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin. The method displayed notable reproducibility. In comparison to UV-spectrophotometric methods, RP-HPLC exhibited superior accuracy, precision, specificity, reproducibility, and sensitivity.

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